

Survey of Fasting Blood Glucose levels in New Medical College Entrants of CMH LMC and IOD

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ABSTRACT

Background & Objectives: Our objective was to measure the fasting blood sugar level (BSL) in new college entrants of CMH Lahore Medical College and Institute of Dentistry (CMH LMC&IOD), and to compare if fasting BSL is affected by positive family history of Diabetes Mellitus (DM).

Study Design: Observational cross-sectional study.

Place & Duration of Study: This study was carried out in CMH LMC&IOD from January, 2018 to August, 2018.

Methods: Non-probability convenient sampling was used to collect data from 67 medical students (MBBS and BDS) after informed consent. The data was entered and analyzed using SPSS 20.

Results: A total of 67 students were included in the study with mean age of 20.13 ± 1.22 years with 44 females and 23 males. The mean fasting BSL was 92.56 ± 10.24 mg/dl. For students with positive family history of DM, mean fasting BSL was 94.10 ± 9.11 and for those with no family history of DM, mean fasting BSL was 90.55 ± 11.40 mg/dl.

Conclusion: Our study concluded that the mean fasting BSL of students with family history of DM was slightly higher as compared to those with no family history of DM but remained statistically insignificant at this sample size.

Keywords: Fasting Blood Glucose, Diabetes, Obesity, Medical Students

INTRODUCTION

There has been a global increase in the prevalence of type 2 diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). This has had a detrimental effect on worldwide health and economies.¹ Of particular health concern is the growing trend of childhood obesity with resultant increase in incidence of T2DM.^{1, 2} The number of overweight and obese children who were under 5 years old worldwide, was 31 million (4.8%) in 1990; this has increased in year 2014 to 42 million (6.1%).³ If this trend continues it is expected that this number may increase to 70 million by 2025.³

Major challenges will be faced by our society, if the incidence and prevalence of type 2 diabetes is not reversed. In the long run, diabetes will affect many more individuals and its cost leads to consumption of enormous resources.⁴

There is strong influence of positive family history on incidence of T2DM in children and young adults. The frequency of positive family history in first and second degree relatives of children with T2DM has been noted to be 74%-100%.⁴ In studies on Pima Indians, scientists have reported at least one diabetic parent in all individuals diagnosed with diabetes. In Pimas, there is increased prevalence of this disease in offsprings of mothers, who had gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) as compared with off-springs of mother without GDM and those who developed diabetes after child birth. Most

of the studies in children, indicate a higher frequency in females. Diagnosis occurs at mean age of 12 and 16 years. A 4 year old Pima Indian was the youngest patient recorded.⁴

It's still under discussion what's the primary defect; insulin hypersecretion or insulin resistance in T2DM in adults. In children with T2DM, the initial abnormality is impaired insulin action and later is beta cell failure. During puberty, there is increased resistance to the action of insulin, resulting in hyperinsulinemia. When pancreatic beta cells are functioning normally, increase insulin secretion occurs to overcome insulin resistance.⁵

OBJECTIVES

- To measure the fasting Blood Glucose Level (BSL) in new college entrants of CMH
- To compare if fasting BSL is related to positive family history of DM.

METHODS

This was a cross-sectional survey carried out in CMH Lahore Medical College, from January, 2018 to August, 2018. MBBS and BDS students willing to participate in the study were asked to fill the questionnaire. Non-probability convenient sampling was used to collect the data from 67 students who consented to be included. The demographic information of students was initially taken and then they were briefed with the purpose of study and procedure to fill the questionnaire. The fasting BSL was done using standardized glucometer. The data was entered and analyzed using SPSS 20. Mean $\pm$ SD was given for normally distributed quantitative variables.

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Table 1. Mean levels of parameters in students

Parameters (n = 67)	Mean ± SD
age (years)	20.13 ± 1.22
weight (kg)	61.52 ± 10.7
height (cm)	167.47 ± 9.03
BMI	21.83 ± 2.49
fasting BSL (mg/dl)	92.56 ± 10.24

Table 2: Mean levels of parameters in girls

Parameters (n = 44)	Mean ± SD
age (years)	19.98 ± 1.15
weight (kg)	61.74 ± 10.8
height (cm)	167.75 ± 9.78
BMI	21.79 ± 2.50
fasting BSL (mg/dl)	92.93 ± 10.54

Table 3: Mean levels of parameters in boys

Parameters (n = 67)	Mean ± SD
age (years)	20.43 ± 1.31
weight (kg)	61.09 ± 10.74
height (cm)	166.92 ± 7.57
BMI	21.89 ± 2.50
fasting BSL (mg/dl)	91.87 ± 9.83

Table 4: Comparison of fasting BSL among students with and without family history of DM.

Parameter	With NO family history of diabetes (n = 29)	With family history of diabetes (n = 38)	p-value
fasting BSL	90.55 ± 11.40	94.10 ± 9.11	0.161 (non-significant)

Table 5: Association between gender and family history of DM.

Family history of DM	Gender		p-value
	Male	Female	
No	6	7	0.04 (significant)
Yes	17	21	

RESULTS

A total of 67 students were included in the study with mean age of 20.13 ± 1.22 years with 44 female and 23 males.

DISCUSSION

In our study population, fasting BSL of students was 92.56 ± 10.24 mg/dl. One study showed that the expected increase in incidence of T2DM over the 1995-2025 time period, in developing countries was 170% as compared to 42% in developed countries.⁶ Increase in incidence of diabetes in youth is a warning sign. In research conducted in 2006, pre diabetes was reported in 2.8 million adolescents and 35% US adults aged 20 years or older.⁷

In a study done in China in 2010, diabetes was reported in 9.4 million adults (20 years or older). The prevalence of diabetes is 3.2% and pre diabetes is 9.0% in ages 20-39 years and 148.2 million adults were reported to be prediabetic.⁸

A survey done in Australia in 2002, prevalence of diabetes was 7.4% and pre-diabetes was 16.4%. Abnormal glucose tolerance in the younger age group in the study (25-34 years) was 5.7%.⁹ A Korean study done in 2006 estimated Korean adults (aged > 20 years) with diabetes were 2.6 million and with impaired fasting glucose were 8.1 million.¹⁰

There is a well-established role of family history as a risk factor of diabetes. In our study fasting BSL in students with family history of diabetes was 94.10 ± 9.11mg/dl. This is higher as compared to those with no family history of diabetes (90.55 ± 11.40mg/dl).

A history of both type 1 and T2DM, have an effect on phenotype of patients with T2DM suggesting a genetic interaction between both types.¹¹ A study done by Waseem et al. showed that male patients with family history of diabetes had higher fasting BSL.¹²

There is scanty data available on the prevalence of the disease in 18-25 years of age. The prevalence of Impaired Fasting Glycemia in 20-39 years age group is 9% in a study conducted in China. In another study conducted on Japanese children, prevalence of prediabetes was noted to be 19.2% in the over-weight children.¹³ In a study conducted in Rawalpindi Pakistan, the prevalence of prediabetes in the youth aged ≤25 years was noted to be 0.88%.¹³ Another study done on school going children in India, showed the prevalence of prediabetes to be 3.7%.¹⁴ While studying the relationship between family history, gender and development of type 2 diabetes, women with a positive family history showed a higher incidence of the disease (p=0.04). A similar study conducted in the

Japanese-Americans also showed similar results in women with positive family history of T2DM ($p=0.018$) in comparison to those with no family history of T2DM.¹⁵

STUDY LIMITATIONS

A small sample size is the biggest limitation of the study. A larger sample size with different participating colleges will be more reliable in finding out the actual state of affairs regarding prevalence and incidence of pre-diabetes and diabetes in young medical students. Moreover oral glucose tolerance test can be included in the workup. There is scanty data available on prevalence of T2DM in young adults in the developing nations of South Asia. It's the need of the time to find out prevalence of pre diabetes in overweight younger population by appropriate screening program so that timely life style changes can be developed and introduced accordingly.

CONCLUSION

Our study concluded that the fasting BSL of students with positive family history of DM although higher as compared to those with no family history of DM was not statistically significant in this study. Also there is association between family history of DM and gender. However it's a small sample size and a larger study would validate the results.

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